

NUMERICAL STUDY OF THE INFLUENCE ON THE MAX TEMPERATURE INSIDE THE RESIN MATRIX COMPOSITES WITH DIFFERENT THICKNESS DURING THE EXOTHERMIC CURING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

Curing is one of the critical processes in the production of carbon fiber reinforced resin matrix composite materials. In this study, a two-way coupling model of heat transfer and curing kinetics reflecting the resin matrix composites in the curing process has been established. Based on the model, a simulation program has been developed independently by using the finite difference method, which can analyse the degree of cure and the temperature fields. By using this program, some numerical simulations for a flat plate of graphite/epoxy resin system are conducted to obtain the temperature and degree of cure fields. Firstly, the thickness of the composites keeps unchanged. The results illustrate that there are two stages of AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy resin system in the curing process. Each stage has a peak temperature. Especially at the second stage, the peak temperature is more obvious. Then the thickness of the composite materials is changed from thin to thick. The max temperature during the exothermic curing process inside the flat plate has been recorded. The result shows that with the increase in thickness of composite materials, the max temperature inside the composites rises slowly then quickly. When the thickness increases closely to the length and width, the max temperature gradually rises smoothly. However, if the thickness keeps on increasing, the max temperature will decrease slowly to a certain temperature and will not change at last. This research provides a certain basis for optimizing the parameters of molding process, mold design and product quality control.

1 INTRODUCTION

As an ideal structural and functional material, carbon fiber reinforced resin matrix composite materials (CFRP) has many advantages such as high specific strength and stiffness, high specific modulus, excellent fatigue and resistance to corrosion and so on. It has become one of the most advanced composite materials and is widely used in the field of aerospace, military industry, chemical industry, etc [1]. In the process of composites production, the resin curing is a very important aspect. When the curing reaction occurs, the resin would emit heat. It may change the original heat transfer case and cause non-uniform temperature distribution. Some residual stress and deformation would exist and this would lead to early destructions of the composites. Therefore, in order to develop reasonable process parameters, it is necessary to conduct a research to study the temperature and curing degree distribution in the process of hot-press forming.

Some scholars have proposed simulation methods on the curing process of resin matrix composites. Bogetti and Giliespie [2] used body-fitted coordinate method combined with finite difference method to take a two-dimensional simulation of the curing process of thick thermosetting composite. Ngos [3] used pure implicit finite element method for a lamina in the non-isothermal condition to study the coupling behaviour of the heat transfer, the curing reaction and the flow process. Sung and Hilton [4],

modelled the curing process using the nonlinear heat conduction finite element method without considering the resin flow. Zuoguang Zhang et al. [5] analyzed the influence by material specific heat capacity, thermal conductivity, density, and package materials on temperature and degree of cure fields using the finite element method. Antonucci [6] proposed a simplified heat transfer model of thick section composites considering the curing exothermic.

There are many restrictions of the research and models mentioned above, such as the simulation only takes two-dimension into consideration, missed the two-way coupled relationship of resin curing and heat transfer and the boundary conditions are demanded. Especially the analysis on the max temperature in the curing process is not comprehensive. This paper establishes a three-dimensional transient numerical analysis model of curing process in resin-based composites molding. Then the temperature and degree of cure fields of a flat plate are obtained. Furthermore, some numerical experiments about the flat plate with different thickness are conducted. The relationship between the thickness of the plat and the max temperature during the exothermic curing inside the flat plate is discussed.

2 MATHEMATICAL MODEL

Curing process of composite material is a complex chemical reaction process. The resin material experience some complex changes from viscous flow state, gel state, glassy state to solid state. And these changes are associated with chemical exothermic phenomenon. In the hot curing process, high temperature gas is the carrier of heat transfer. As the gas temperature rises and begins to flow, the heat will transfer from the outside to the inside of the composite material. At the same time, curing reaction gradually occurs in the resin [7]. In this process, the temperature of resin will affect its curing rate, while the heat from the curing resin will also affect the temperature distribution too. Figure 1 shows the relationship between them.

Figure 1: The relationship between heat transmission and curing reaction in hot-press process.

Thus, it can be seen that the temperature and degree of cure of the resin are correlated. To make their relationship clear, it was necessary to comprehend the chemical model, including a heat transfer model and cure kinetic model. Due to the thermoforming process involving many factors and some of them have little impact on the process, this study had the following premises:

- (1) Resin and fiber were treated as a whole material which was a homogeneous anisotropic material on the macro scale;
- (2) The heat transmission caused by resin flowing was ignored;
- (3) The temperature of the resin and fiber was the same when they were located in the same internal of the composite materials;
- (4) The influence of the internal composite porosity was ignored.
- (5) Irrespective of the resin carbonization at high temperature.

2.1 Heat transfer model

The temperature field of resin-based composite curing is a heat conduction problem with non-linear inner heat source, and the inner heat source comes from the exothermal reactions of matrix resin. Considering the inner heat resource, we can use Fourier heat equation and the energy conservative relations to establish the three-dimensional transient equation of heat conduction. It is thus given by:

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = k_x \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + k_y \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + k_z \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} + \dot{q} \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the density of the material, C_p is the specific heat capacity of the material, T is temperature, t is time, k_x , k_y , k_z are three heat transfer coefficients in three main directions and \dot{q} which has something to do with the curing rate is the heat form the resin curing in unit time. The definition of \dot{q} is showed as the following equation [7]:

$$\dot{q} = \rho(1-V_f)H_R \frac{d\alpha}{dt} \quad (2)$$

where V_f is fiber volume content and H_R is the total reaction heat released form the curing of a unit quantity. α is the degree of resin curing and $\frac{d\alpha}{dt}$ is the resin curing rate.

According to the above two equations, it could be seen that the degree of cure and temperature coupling with each other. The density and specific heat capacity of composite materials could be obtained by using the mixing law show in equations (3, 4). While the heat conductivity of composite material depends primarily on combinations of resin and fiber. It is generally anisotropic and can be calculated using the volume weighted average method. Calculation method is shown as the following equations [9]:

$$\rho_p = V_f \rho_f + (1-V_f) \rho_r \quad (3)$$

$$C_p = V_f C_{pf} + (1-V_f) C_{pr} \quad (4)$$

$$k_p = V_f k_{pf} + (1-V_f) k_{pr} \quad (k = k_x, k_y, k_z) \quad (5)$$

where ρ_p , C_p , k_p is the density, specific heat capacity and heat transfer coefficients of the composite. ρ_f , C_f , k_f is the density, specific heat capacity and heat transfer coefficients of the fiber. ρ_r , C_r , k_r is the density, specific heat capacity and heat transfer coefficients of the resin. V_f is fiber volume content.

2.2 Curing kinetic model

Curing process of the composite materials is a complex chemical reaction. Up to now, the kinetic model has been divided into two main models, phenomenological model and mechanism model [10, 11]. While, the former one is wildy applied. Based on the curing trait, Kamal proposed the autocatalytic model [12]:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = (K_1 + K_2 \alpha^m)(1-\alpha)^n \quad (6)$$

$$K_i = A_i e^{-\frac{E_i}{RT}} \quad (i = 1, 2) \quad (7)$$

where K_i is the speed constant and A_i is the pre-exponential factor. E_i is the activation energy. The m and n are reaction orders.

In this model, when m plus n is 2, meaning that the reaction order is two, the above equation have been wildy used to describe the isothermal curing reaction kinetics of unsaturated polyester resins and epoxy resin. It's necessary to measure two curing kinetic parameters of the equation, the curing state and curing rate, in the same time. A method that is often used to measure those two curing kinetic parameters is thermo analysis technology, such as differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) [13]. When the kinetic parameters are obtained, it can be used to predict the degree of cure for any temperature

history by the following equation:

$$\alpha = \int_0^t \left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt} \right) dt \quad (8)$$

3 CALCULATION PARAMETERS

In this paper, the finite difference method was used to detect the mathematical model described above and the corresponding thermal curing simulation program was developed. The non-uniform grid technology was adopted to mesh the model. The adopted autoclave temperature cycle presented in Figure 2 is a two-stage cycle.

Figure 2: Autoclave temperature cycle.

The composite material used for simulation is AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy resin system where the thickness is 20 mm, the length and width are both 300 mm. The material properties of AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy are given in Table 1 and the curing kinetics parameters are given in Table 2. The curing kinetics equation is as [14].

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\alpha}{dt} = (K_1 + K_2\alpha)(1-\alpha)(0.47-\alpha) & \alpha \leq 0.3 \\ \frac{d\alpha}{dt} = K_3(1-\alpha) & \alpha > 0.3 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$$K_1 = A_1 e^{-\frac{E_1}{RT}}; \quad K_2 = A_2 e^{-\frac{E_2}{RT}}; \quad K_3 = A_3 e^{-\frac{E_3}{RT}}$$

Parameters	Value
ρ [kg/m ³]	21.7
C_p [J/(kg•K)]	20.3
K_z [W/(m•K)]	0.4135
$k_x, k_y/k_z$	1,5,10

Table 1: Material properties of AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy.

Parameters	Value
A_1 [min ⁻¹]	2.102×10^9
A_2 [min ⁻¹]	-2.014×10^9
A_3 [min ⁻¹]	1.960×10^5
E_1 [J/mol]	8.07×10^4
E_2 [J/mol]	7.78×10^4

E_3	[J/mol]	5.66×10^4
R	[J/(mol·K)]	8.3143
H_R	[J/kg]	198.6×10^3
V_f	–	0.5

Table 2: Cure kinetics parameters for AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Basic result

Using the program, temperature and degree of cure profiles at the geometrical center of the composites could be obtained as shown in Figure 3. It can be seen that there is an inflection point in the degree of cure profile. The curing process is divided into two stages by this point. This is consistent with the epoxy resin curing kinetics of equation 9. In the profile, there are two peaks. The first peak temperature is 116.86 °C at 34 min. It is 0.86 °C higher than the temperature of the air. The second peak temperature is 179.45 °C at 118 min. It is 2.45 °C higher than the temperature of the air. The reason for these two peaks is obviously that the curing reaction is an exothermic phenomenon. From the degree of cure profile, these two stages are both presented as "slow-fast-slow" trend. And the amount of the release heat of second peak is higher than the first peak. It could be seen that the heat released by the reaction is proportional to the curing rate by equation (2). Since the curing rate is low at the first stage, the heat released by the resin curing reaction is less. The peak can not be obviously seen at the first stage. While, at the second stage, a clear peak temperature exists in the profiles because the released heat is much greater than the first stage as the curing rate is higher.

Figure 3: Temperature and degree of cure profiles.

4.2 Influence of the thickness

In the curing process, the resin would release heat which changes the original temperature field distribution. If the amount of the released heat is too large, it will make the temperature of the composites increased sharply. It is likely to make resin carbonized, resulting in the failure of the composites. For the curing exotherm, the thickness of the composite material is one of the key influences. In this section, a series of numerical simulations with different thickness of the composites are conducted. The thickness is changed from thin to thick while the other parameters are unchanged. Here carbonization of the resin is not considered.

As mentioned above, the max temperature of AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy resin system appears at the second exothermic peak. Figure 4 shows the max temperature varied with thickness of composites. It can be seen that with the increase of thickness of composite materials the max temperature inside the composites rises slowly then quickly. When the thickness increases closely to the length and width, the max temperature gradually rises smoothly. And when the thickness is increased to 400mm, the max temperature reached the highest. That is 241.21 °C, 64.21 °C higher than the air. However, if the thickness keeps on increasing, the max temperature does not rise, but decrease slowly. At last, the max

temperature will be keep at 234°C. The max temperature will no longer increases with the thickness change.

Figure 4: The relationship between the thickness and the max temperature.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a two-way coupled model of heat transfer and curing kinetics in resin-based composite curing process, and develops a simulation program of curing and temperature field based on FDM. By using this program, some numerical simulations for a flat plate of graphite/epoxy resin system are conducted. The simulation results of a flat plate illustrate that there are two stages of AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy resin system in the curing process. As the curing reaction is an exothermic phenomenon, each stage has a peak temperature. Especially at the second stage, the peak temperature is more obvious because the curing rate is higher than that at the first stage. When the thickness of composites changes from thin to thick, the max temperature inside the flat plate changes too. With the increase in thickness of composite materials, the max temperature rises slowly then quickly. When the thickness increases closely to the length and width, the max temperature gradually rises smoothly. However, if the thickness keeps on increasing, the max temperature will decrease slowly to a certain temperature and will not change at last. This research provides a certain basis for optimizing the molding process parameters, mold design and product quality control.

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